

NOVASOIL

INNOVATIVE BUSINESS MODELS FOR SOIL HEALTH

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Baseline conceptual framework

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QUALITY ASSURANCE PROCEDURES

This document has been shared to the consortium in order to ensure their quality and to include a multidisciplinary point of view. Following a description of the different reviews can be found

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1 Executive summary

The European NOVASOIL project seeks to create a conceptual framework for sustainable business models centred around soil health. This document serves as a foundation for understanding soil health within the context of environmental sustainability, supporting the project's goal of promoting investment in soil health through innovative business solutions. This summary outlines key definitions, approaches, and variables essential for stakeholders interested in developing soil-health-based business models.

The primary objective of the NOVASOIL project is to highlight the societal and environmental benefits of investing in soil health. The project will develop a "toolbox" to analyse various business models that promote soil health, particularly across different land uses, climatic conditions, and sectors such as agriculture and agroforestry. This toolbox will include categorization models based on best practices, sustainable management, and EU policies, with a focus on profitability and environmental effectiveness.

The project also aims to develop frameworks and methodologies that stakeholders, such as farmers, researchers, and policymakers, can apply to assess the financial viability and ecological benefits of soil health investments. By integrating a wide range of stakeholders into its research, the project seeks to establish a community of practice to drive interest and knowledge about soil health investments.

NOVASOIL identifies four primary business models to enhance soil health:

- **Payment for Ecosystem Services (PES):** These models focus on monetizing ecosystem services like carbon sequestration, water provision, and flood control.
- **Value Chain Models:** These contracts compensate farmers for sustainable products, linking public goods like clean water or reduced emissions to private products.
- **Carbon Credits:** This model involves trading carbon credits, contributing to climate change mitigation.
- **Collective Implementation:** This involves farmer cooperatives and collective actors working together to promote sustainable practices.

These models are flexible and often used in combination, allowing for tailored solutions across different regions and contexts.

The concept of soil health is defined through physical, chemical, and biological indicators that affect ecosystem services, such as food production, water filtration, and carbon sequestration. Key soil health indicators include soil organic carbon, soil texture, bulk density, pH levels, and biodiversity metrics such as microbial biomass and earthworm diversity. The NOVASOIL project emphasizes the need for robust monitoring systems to ensure soil health improvements are tracked effectively over time.

Involving stakeholders in business model design is crucial for the success of soil health initiatives. The NOVASOIL project employs a participatory

approach, integrating the perspectives of farmers, policymakers, and investors to develop business models that align with stakeholder needs. The project also highlights the role of technology in soil monitoring, advocating for in-situ monitoring, remote sensing, and data analysis tools to optimize decision-making.

The framework supports the use of innovative digital tools to track business model performance, thus making it easier for policymakers and landowners to assess the long-term impacts of soil health investments. The development of a "toolbox" for stakeholders will allow them to model and predict the viability of various soil health business models across different ecosystems and regulatory environments.

NOVASOIL aligns its business models with several EU policies, such as the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), the Green Deal, and the Farm to Fork strategy. The project also anticipates the impact of future legislation, including the proposed EU Soil Health Law, which aims to restore degraded ecosystems and promote sustainable soil management practices.

The regulatory framework will be crucial for the success of soil health business models, as these laws are expected to mandate the integration of soil health within broader environmental and agricultural policies. Legal considerations such as transaction costs, compliance with environmental legislation, and equity among stakeholders will be factored into the design of business models.

The NOVASOIL project aims to transform the current conceptual framework into an operational tool that supports the design of business models for sustainable soil management. This framework will not only contribute to environmental sustainability but also offer new revenue streams for farmers and landowners. Through its innovative approach, which blends scientific research, stakeholder engagement, and technological integration, NOVASOIL is set to become a pivotal project in promoting soil health across Europe.

For stakeholders, this document offers a detailed guide on the variables to consider when designing and implementing soil-health-based business models, emphasizing both economic feasibility and environmental sustainability.

2 Objectives of the document

2.1 Objective

The purpose of this document is to establish an initial conceptual framework for the project NOVASOIL, which will serve as a foundation for interpreting the project's activities and connecting its objectives, approach, and relevant information on the topic.

This first version of the framework employs a structured and extensive literature review approach to support the project's planned activities. It also aims to outline the project's scope and relevant definitions, as well as explore the preliminary logic of the initial conceptual framework. This framework will

be further developed and refined during WPI activities and throughout the project's entirety.

The main objective of the document is to establish the basis of the most updated knowledge about business models that take care of soil health. This document allows you to be informed about the most recent scientific literature on the topic, including classic concepts, as well as discussing issues related to certain aspects of the topic.

2.2 Why develop a single comprehensive baseline report

The NOVASOIL strategy is to analyse the different benefits for society and the environment from investment in soil health. Their integration is being pursued through the development of the unified conceptual framework developed at the beginning of the project and tested/ improved through and by continuous interaction with a wide range of stakeholders in an actor-led policy support/ development process. By the end of the project, it is expected to achieve the transformation of the initial framework into an effective operational tool able to support decision-making in business model solutions to different case studies.

2.3 Outline

As this document is the starting point to develop the contents of NOVASOIL, the next section will report the key objectives and approach of the project and also aim to justify the identification of the framework. Section 3 will illustrate the general framework components and interactions. Section 4 gets into details of methods and stakeholder engagement. Section 5 discusses the methods to analyse business models and situations, with support implementation, with a special emphasis on stakeholders' participation.

3 Project objectives and approach

3.1 Objectives

The general objective of the NOVASOIL project is to highlight the benefits for society and the environment from the investment in soil health. The main expected outcome of the project is a toolbox for the analysis of the suitability of different business cases that promote soil health. This toolbox will be based on a set of good examples from Europe and other countries and the needs and demands of society. The toolbox will include a categorisation of the models and business cases considering a) sustainable soil management under different land uses and climatic conditions; b) products based on practices promoting soil health; c) consumption and certification practices conducive; d) the reuse of land and e) sustainable soil management in the context of the EU Taxonomy Regulation.

The NOVASOIL multi-actor and multidisciplinary team bring together 16 partners in 10 countries, covering representative typologies of actors involved in soil health and business models (farmer organisation, research institutions, consultancy companies, etc).

Specific objectives are:

SO1. Portfolio development of multiple dimensions of business cases and good examples for investing in soil health in Europe and outside Europe.

SO2. Analysis of current models in the world that allow creation of new incentives and new revenues from healthy soils considering the categories cited previously.

SO3. Implement a co-development approach in the modelling that promotes soil health.

SO4. Develop a prototype toolbox of incentives and a testing network.

SO5. Analysis of current policies and technologies related to soil health and providing a revenue for farmers.

SO6. Develop a Community of Practice around soil health investors and key actors.

SO7. Increase the interest in soil health through a Digital Marketing Strategy plan.

3.2 Concept and approach of the framework

Figure 1 Business creation strategy

3.3 Expected contents of the final framework

According to the GA, the final version of the framework will include the following:

- A. A list of successful experiences and good practices related to the innovative business models based on the case studies developed and presented in a usable form as examples for land users. This will include a detailed description of the different characteristics of the business model for replication.

- B. Improved case studies through the most sustainable and efficient management practices
- C. A “design guide” including political, socioeconomic and environmental indicators intended as a systematic comprehensive process for the design of the sustainable businesses
- D. Documentation, training and supporting materials

3.4 Scope and definitions

This section summarises some definitions and topics related to the purposes of the NOVASOIL project. The systematic glossary will be developed in the next steps of the project

• 2.4.1 Case study

In the NOVASOIL project, a case study is intended as a case of real implementation (or intended) of a specific business model related to soil health in an area or region. It can involve several participating actors as farms, public administration, investors, etc, and several individual cases of implementation of the same business model. The case studies in the NOVASOIL project are implemented under different land uses with different soil health targets.

• 2.4.2 Business model

A business model is a framework that outlines how a company operates, creates, delivers, and captures value. It describes the overall strategy of a business and provides a roadmap for how the company will generate revenue and make a profit (Osterwalder & Pigneur, 2010; Teece, 2010). The business model is an essential tool for entrepreneurs and businesses to identify and evaluate the viability of their ideas, products, and services in the market.

A business model typically includes several key aspects that should be highlighted to describe how the business creates, delivers, and captures value. Some of the most important elements of a business model are:

- 1) Customer segments - The different groups of people and organizations that the company aims to reach and serve through its products and services.
- 2) Value proposition - The bundle of products and services that create value for a specific customer segment
- 3) Channels - How a company communicates with and reaches its customer segments to deliver a value proposition
- 4) Customer relationship - The types of relationships a company establishes with specific customer segments
- 5) Revenue streams - The cash a company generates from each customer segment
- 6) Key resources - The most important assets required to make a business model working
- 7) Key activities - The most important activities a company must do to make its business model works
- 8) Key partnership - The network of suppliers and partners that make the business model working

9) Cost structure - All costs incurred to operate a business model

• 2.4.3 Soil health

Soil health refers to the ability of soil to sustain and improve the biological, chemical, and physical properties that support plant growth and other ecosystem functions (Doran and Zeiss, 2000). A healthy soil is one that can support a diverse range of plant and animal life, maintain its structure and fertility, retain and release water and nutrients, and resist degradation and erosion. Soil health is important for maintaining ecosystem services such as food production, water filtration, and carbon sequestration, as well as for supporting the resilience of agricultural and natural systems to environmental stresses such as drought, flooding, and climate change (Bot & Benites, 2015).

• 2.4.4 Technologies

Technologies refer to the tools, techniques, and methods used to develop or create goods, services, or systems (Britannica, The Editors of Encyclopaedia. "technology". Encyclopaedia Britannica, 31 Aug. 2022, [link](#). Accessed 10 April 2023.). Technologies can be physical devices or software programs that facilitate communication, data processing, and the automation of various tasks. They can also include techniques and methods for problem-solving, decision-making, and the management of resources. The development and use of technology have transformed many aspects of human life, from how we communicate and work to how we travel and access information. There are several technologies related to soil health that have been developed in recent years. Some of these technologies include: soil sensors, satellites, drones, Decision Support Systems, etc.

• 2.4.5 Incentives

Incentives are stimuli or rewards offered to people in order to motivate them to perform certain desired actions or behaviours. Incentives can be positive (rewards) or negative (punishments) and can be used in different contexts, such as in economics, education, business, and politics, among others (Ouvrard & Strenger, 2019).

For example, in a company, an incentive could be a bonus or a salary increase for achieving certain goals or targets. In education, an incentive could be a prize or recognition for good academic performance. In politics, an incentive could be the promise of a reform or a particular benefit in exchange for voting for a certain candidate.

There are different incentives to be considered in a contract: 1) payment structure (fixed fee, not-to-exceed, etc); 2) Commitment to Design and Total Costs of Ownership (TCO); 3) Milestones, amounts at risks, milestones credits (project plans and timelines based on milestones); 4) Enhanced credits for extended misses; 5) Holdback; 6) Reimbursement for retained costs; 7) Right to pursue damages; 8) Right to put Project in hold; 9) Step-in rights and; 10) Termination and Repayment Remedies.

In the context of soil health, incentives can be used to encourage farmers and land managers to adopt practices that promote healthy soils.

For instance, governments may offer financial incentives, such as tax credits or grants, to farmers who use practices like conservation tillage, cover cropping, and nutrient management that promote soil health. Similarly, private companies may offer premium prices for crops grown using soil-friendly practices, providing farmers with a financial incentive to adopt these practices. The practices are established regarding scientific knowledge at local level in order to set up a hierarchy between practices.

In addition to financial incentives, educational and technical assistance programs can be established to help farmers learn about and implement soil health-promoting practices. These programs can provide farmers with the knowledge and skills needed to successfully adopt and maintain healthy soil practices, and can help to overcome any perceived barriers to adoption.

Overall, incentives are an important tool in promoting soil health, as they can help to encourage the widespread adoption of soil-friendly practices and help to build a more sustainable and resilient agricultural system (Piñeiro et al., 2020).

4 Framework components and interactions

4.1 Context features

4.1.1 Introduction

This section of the document details information on the different variables to be taken into account to achieve the project objectives. The scope of these variables can be very broad, since the concepts can be related to a very large set of characteristics, from the situation of soil pressure due to climate change to current market trends. Nevertheless, many of these variables are influenced by the existence of an economic system related to the Earth's natural resources, the bioeconomy. Also, the categories included here may contain different kinds of variables, state variables as the market situation, flow variables as ecosystem services.

4.1.2 State of the soil health and ecosystem

World soils and our society face difficult challenges with a projected population of 9.1 billion by 2050 (Godfray et al. 2010). 95% of our food is directly and indirectly produced on our soils (FAO,2015). Soils also contribute to the production of raw materials or crops for biofuel and fiber (Bagnall et al. 2021). Agricultural land will need to produce more food, feed, and fiber in the next 50 years than in the previous 5000 years combined (Stott & Moebius-Clune 2017). The Food Mission Board (MB) and the European Commission's Joint Research Centre (JRC) reviewed the current state of Europe soils, which resulted in 60-70% of EU soils being unhealthy, with an uncertain percentage of soils unhealthy due to poorly quantified pollution issues. 65-75% of agricultural soils, nitrogen values exceed critical values showing an excess of fertilizer applications in EU soils affecting air and water quality, claiming

strongest livestock farming reductions in very high-density regions. (EUROSTAT,2020; SOER, 2020, de Vries et al.,2021).

Soil organic matter, measured as soil organic carbon (SOC), has been lost through soil microbial metabolic activity and aggressive management practices as the plough, damaging the soil structure and disturbing soil functions related with SOC sequestration and storage. LUCAS soil data show that cultivated and permanent crops have the lowest SOC concentrations of all major land cover classes, compared to permanent grasslands that are 2.4 times higher (Hiederer & Castillo, 2018). The trend in carbon stocks shows a decrease in the land use changes analysis and shows that about 60% of agricultural areas experienced a decrease in the average carbon stock.

According to Panagos et al. (2015,2020) and Borelli et al. (2017), non-permanent crops and bare soils have the highest soil erosion rates. Mean soil erosion by water for the EU is 2.46 t ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹, resulting in a total annual soil loss of 970 Mt. On the other hand, wind erosion in the EU is 530.000 t ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹. Approximately 23% of cropland and 30% of non-agricultural areas are under the effect of this degradation affecting soil health. According to JRC, soil compaction is a problem that affects 33% of European soils, of which 20% moderately so.

In terms of soil pollution, determining the entire area affected by this problem is a challenging purpose. There are multitudes of ways in which soil can become contaminated and have its functions altered. Numerous studies show the impact of pollution on soil, but it is difficult to assess the area. 21% of European agricultural soils that have cadmium excesses exceeding drinking water limits. 2.93 M km², i.e. 5% of European land where critical loads are exceeded for acidification and 2.65 M km² are subjected to nitrogen deposition leading to eutrophication (Posh et al., 2018). Problems associated with plastics, sewage sludge, pesticides and trace elements caused a potential risk to human and biodiversity health and are a current problem too.

While the function of soil for food production was well recognised, the conservation and improvement of soil to provide ecosystem services has not been recognised until recent years. The term "ecosystem service" (ES), is defined as the set of goods and services that human societies obtain from the planet's ecosystems. According to CICES (Common Classification of Ecosystem Services), there are several types of ecosystem services: (a) provisioning services;(b) regulating and maintenance services; and (c) cultural services. Soils in natural ecosystems are part of a dynamic system that is self-regulated by known soil functions, which regulate and support the way in which they provide ecosystem services (CEC, 2006; Hannam and Boer, 2004; Adhikari and Hartemink, 2016). We have considerable knowledge about soil formation and distribution, but our understanding of soil functions and how they provide ecosystem services is scarce. Soils are a major component in most ES-related studies, as well as being essential in policy decisions taking economic importance in many regions (Hewitt et al,2015; Daily et al. 1997). The provision of soil ecosystem services depends on soil properties and their interactions, influenced by its use and management. Water and wind

erosion, soil organic carbon and biodiversity loss lead to soil degradation, which is a global serious problem for food security and ecosystem sustainability (Adhikari and Hartemink, 2016).

Soil health is an ambiguous concept that depends on the point of view from which it can be effectively treated. Physical, biological and chemical factors have been described in the literature in order to evaluate soils according to certain criteria. Historically, the description of the concept has focused on different agricultural lands and food production, but it is now known that soil health plays very important roles in water regulation and quality, human health, climate change, biodiversity status, etc.

Assessing and defining soil health today requires updating previously used methodologies. The current global state influences soil functions in different ways. Global change drivers such as global temperature increase, carbon dioxide increase, changes in precipitation patterns or increased frequency of droughts and floods, are some of the factors to be taken into account. European soils are under a big pressure in different ways of soil degradation; threats are mainly the following (Guo,2021):

- High rate of urbanization, soil sealing and replacement as well as pollution and industrialization.
- The relentless expansion of agriculture using chemical fertilizers, heavy machinery and unsustainable management practices
- Intensive forestry activities particularly affecting woodland species and forest habitats
- Drastic climate changes cause weather extremes.
- Land-related businesses that are established without taking into account future trends, with very short lifespans or not following established sustainable management practices; increase soil degradation.
- Improper water management, reuse and irrigation.
- Overexploitation and uncompensated consumption of natural resources

Furthermore, the concept of healthy soils must be considered through useful measurements known as soil health indicators, which are sensitive to changes and represent the different properties of the soil. The most commonly used soil health indicators are the following:

Physical indicators: soil texture, soil structure, bulk density, water drainage and storage, soil type, stoniness and macroporosity.

Biological indicators: vegetation cover, soil organic carbon matter, enzymatic activity, microbial respiration, macrofauna (earthworms) and mesofauna (collembola)

Chemical indicators : pH, nutrient content, nutrient availability, cation exchange capacity, heavy metal content, salt content and trace elements.

4.1.3 Business sites related soil health

Three main areas have been identified regarding soil health business:

- Agriculture is the main sector where new business models could be implemented. Also, agriculture is the sector which has the most developed markets and policies, and the variety of market opportunities is very wide.
- Agroforestry is an important growing sector to develop in the soil health framework. Time and types of production are different from agriculture, this includes how we treat the soil and generate ecosystem services and, consequently, soil health improvement.
- Urban, semi-urban and green zones are a sector with poor information about business models but can be developed. There is literature explaining that we can obtain numerous benefits through good management of these zones, improving the cultural ecosystem services but also soil health.

4.1.4 Technologies

The term "technology" pertains to the vast array of tools and systems utilised to execute a business. The collection of available technologies dictates the potential for production, costs and profitability of various business models, and possibilities for soil monitoring and management practices. This also includes the implementation of information technology that is suitable for minimising input usage, managing transactions, and monitoring outcomes and the environment.

From the point of view of NOVASOIL, technology is relevant under three main aspects:

- The set of technologies to increase knowledge and demonstrate the benefits of investing in soil health, assist in decision-making and creating targeted policies.
- Potential technologies for monitoring, evaluation and viability of soil health and the ecosystem services are provided. There are many forms of soil monitoring, but the main problem they face is the high sampling and analysis capacity needed to be fully effective. In addition to this, sampling and analysis is carried out on different land uses and soil types, thus adding complexity. Easier is to evaluate a soil if the potential threats are known. For the monitoring are three main possibilities: in situ monitoring, sampling and monitoring by earth observation techniques.
- Information technologies that help to implement and adapt new business models to the user, analysing the existing business models around the world and offering the best option.

The NOVASOIL project has the third point as the most important, since it bases the principal objective in developing an operational soil health business cases framework supporting the analysis of existing business cases that promote soil health and the design of more effective ones. This is accompanied by the first and second points, improving solutions to facilitate policy-making, stakeholder interplay and incentive soil health investment.

The combination of all of these points can also bring completely new ways in producing and implementing innovative solutions in business models and soil health, also, improving existing soil management practices and ecosystem services provided. In this way, all information obtained from the use of this technology's applications will be implemented in a toolbox.

4.1.5 Monitoring technologies

Soil health is a critical factor in agricultural productivity and environmental sustainability. The health of the soil impacts not only crop yield but also the ecosystem services that support the broader natural environment. Soil degradation can result from various factors, including chemical contamination, overuse, and erosion. As such, monitoring soil health is vital in maintaining sustainable agricultural practices and mitigating environmental damage.

Compliance technologies have emerged as a useful tool in monitoring soils. These technologies are designed to assess the impact of agricultural practices on the soil and provide recommendations for sustainable land use. By using these technologies, farmers can track the effectiveness of their practices in improving soil health and take corrective measures if necessary.

One example of a compliance technology is precision agriculture, which uses GPS mapping and remote sensing technologies to assess soil quality and recommend appropriate fertilisation and irrigation practices. This technology provides land managers with real-time data on soil health, which they can use to make informed decisions on land use and crop management.

In addition to compliance technologies, remote sensing technologies such as satellite imaging can be used to monitor soil health (Table 1). These technologies can provide a comprehensive view of soil health over a large area and identify potential issues that may require further investigation. The current state of the art of technologies related to Earth observation techniques allows predictions very close to reality. One of the objectives to be achieved is the measurement of soil data and soil condition without the need for on-site sampling.

Soil data targeted	Methods	Input	Output
Soil moisture estimation	SVM, ANN	Spaceborne remote sensing data	Estimated soil moisture
	SVM, ANN	Air temperature, relative humidity, average solar radiation	
	DBN, MLP	Evapotranspiration, leaf area index, meteorological information, land surface temperature	
Drought prediction	SVR, drought index	Area index, intensity index, ridge position index, western ridge point index, northern boundary position index	Standardized precipitation evapotranspiration index
	DT, RF	Automatic synoptic observation system data, drought indicator, remote sensing data	Drought accuracy
Water depth	LSTM	Irrigation volume, rainfall volume, evaporation volume, temperature	Water table depth
Soil organic carbon	MARS, ANN, SVM, PLSR, RF	Spectral measurements, total carbon, total nitrogen, pH	Soil organic carbon
Soil mapping workflow	k-NN, SVM, RF	Soil texture, horizon, depth, mottle depth, soil moisture, landform	Soil mapping covariates

Soil erosion and remediation	DT	geological formation, soil type, annual precipitation, elevation, inclination, vegetation	Soil erosion prediction
	RF	topographic wetness index, stream power index, transport capacity index, slope, curvature, relief elevation, land use	Erosion process class
Soil contaminants	RF, ERF, SVM, MLP	high-resolution aerial imaging of arsenic contaminated agricultural field	Soil risk level
	MPL, ANN, MSP, LR	moisture, organic carbon, total carbon, total nitrogen, total phosphorus, available phosphorus, loss on ignition	PAH bioavailability

Table 1. Summary of existing technologies/models by type of soil data targeted (derived from Fan et al., 2022)

4.1.6 Remote sensing

Remote sensing technologies have the potential to optimise the use of resources in on-farm inspections by reducing the need for on-the-spot controls and enabling more targeted deployments of inspectors and management practices. Combining imagery with other data sources could enhance the effectiveness of the control regime. For example, Light Detection and Ranging (LIDAR) is an active remote sensing system that can measure vegetation height over wide areas. By using pulsed lasers to measure distances to the earth, LIDAR can be used in conjunction with remote sensing to evaluate eligible grassland areas under the pro-rata method for permanent grassland. Additionally, when used with crop identification software, LIDAR can potentially provide a cost-effective means of meeting the greening crop diversification inspection requirements within a shorter period. However, cloud cover in these inaccessible areas can limit the reliability of this method.

Figure 2 Common remote sensing technologies and products related with soil health

4.1.7 Sentinel data

In addition to LIDAR and other remote sensing technologies, satellite imagery like Sentinel missions are also revolutionising the field of land monitoring. Sentinel-2, for example, offers unprecedented opportunities for global agricultural monitoring by providing 12 spectral bands and 10-20 m spatial resolution coverage with a 5-day revisit frequency. This level of detail and frequency allows for continual monitoring of soil properties and crop conditions, enabling farmers to assess land use, predict harvests, monitor seasonal changes, droughts, and other factors that can impact crop yield and soil health. By leveraging the power of satellite imagery and other remote sensing technologies, farmers and land managers can gain valuable insights

into their operations and make more informed decisions about how to manage their land sustainably. This can ultimately lead to improved soil health, increased crop yields, and more efficient use of resources.

4.1.8 Drones and UAVs

Drones are becoming an increasingly valuable tool in land monitoring, particularly in areas where traditional on-the-spot controls are difficult due to limited physical access. These aerial vehicles can provide accurate and detailed information on soil health and crop conditions, allowing farmers and land managers to make more informed decisions about their operations. However, the use of drones is subject to legal limitations in each Member State. In some cases, landowners may need to provide permission for drone flights and operators may need to be registered.

Despite these challenges, drones offer a number of benefits for land monitoring. For example, they can be used for targeted campaigns in specific areas where detailed information is needed, such as areas with suspected soil erosion or nutrient deficiencies. Additionally, drones can provide high-resolution imagery that is not affected by cloud cover and other objects like trees or piles, which can be a significant issue when relying on satellite or aerial imagery.

Moreover, drones can be equipped with a range of sensors, such as thermal cameras or multispectral sensors, that can provide even more detailed information about soil health and crop conditions. Drones and cameras can measure these properties indirectly, by analysing the spectral signature of the soil or plants and applying different models. These measurements can be made using various sensors such as optical, thermal, and radar sensors (Table 2).

Soil properties	Plant properties
Soil moisture content	Vegetation indices (e.g. NDVI, EVI, SAVI)
Soil temperature	Photosynthetic activity
Soil organic matter content	Canopy cover
Soil texture	Biomass and productivity
Soil pH	Plant height
Soil compaction	Water stress
Soil salinity	Leaf nitrogen content
Soil nutrient content (e.g. N, P, K)	Leaf area index (LAI)

Table 2. *Common soil and plant properties measured by the use of drones and UAVs technologies.*

This information can be used to create detailed maps of soil properties and crop health, which can help farmers and land managers to identify areas that require targeted interventions or to monitor changes over time. Overall, while there are legal limitations to the use of drones in land monitoring, their potential to provide accurate and detailed information makes them a valuable tool for sustainable land management.

Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) are used as an environmental remote sensing application to reduce the data gaps between in situ data collection and satellite resolution. The photogrammetric image processing enables the creation of Digital Terrain Models (DTMs) and ortho-image mosaics with very high resolution on a sub-decimetre level. It can be used to quantify gully and badland erosion in 2D and 3D, as well as for landscape development over very large areas (D'Oleire-Oltmanns et al., 2012). UAVs are considered a very good tool for the management, digitisation and analysis of high-precision agricultural systems but are still too expensive and the processing of images needs skills and time to be used by a conventional user (M.R.Barbosa-Junior et al., 2022). Collected data can be exploited for an almost continuous (in space and time) monitoring of the exploitation resources, allowing better decision making with higher precision, optimising crop yield, and making predictions about the future to prevent the spread of pests and diseases.

4.2 Monitoring of business models' impacts

NOVASOIL is focused on the identification and implementation of business models to demonstrate the benefits and co-benefits of investing in soil health that allows a substantial improvement in decision-making. To maintain these business models in their optimal state, continuous monitoring and evaluation of the state of the soil is needed. Thus, some soil health indicators and their possible monitoring techniques are included below.

4.2.1 Monitoring Soil Health: key variables

According to the recent EEA report, the following table shows the main soil threats, which are monitored by a set of well-established, easily understandable indicators, fed by soil physical, chemical and biological parameters (Table 3).

Soil threat	Indicator	Thresholds	Comment
Soil organic carbon loss			
Cropland	Falling below optimal SOC level	Light soils: <1.2% SOC Medium soils: 1.2-1.9% SOC Heavy soils: >1.9% SOC	SOC: clay ratio (Johannes et al., 2017): optimum SOC content as 10% of the clay content/vulnerability limit
Nutrient loss			
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical levels of mineral nitrogen (agricultural land)	NH ₃ in air: 1-3mg NH ₃ /m ³	Mineral N: sum of available NH ₄ and NO ₃
		NO ₃ in groundwater: 50mg NO ₃ /l	
		N in surface water: 1.0-2.5mg N/l	
Forest land	N limitation based on exceedance of C: N ratio	C: N ratio 20-25	Forest floor organic layer
		Leakage from forests: 1m	
Agriculture	Falling below optimal phosphorus	P concentration: 25-35mg/kg (optimal)	Extractable P concentration < optimum (value range refers to Mehlich 3-ICP; also available P-Bray PI and Olsen P)
		P limitation based on exceedance of N:P ratio	
Forest land		N:P ratio >25 (deciduous forests)	
Acidification			
Agriculture	Exceedance of critical pH levels	pH<4.5 -4.7 (critical)	Risk of Al toxicity
		pH<5-5.5 (avoid)	Limited availability of Ca, Mg and

Forest land	Exceedance of critical inorganic Al levels	Base cation: Al ratio= 1 (0.5-2.0)	Ca ²⁺ , Mg ²⁺ and K ⁺
Soil pollution			
All land uses	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from heavy metals and organic pollutants	Cd, Cu, Pb, Zn, As, Hg, Ni, Cr	Country-specific values vary broadly and are not necessarily comparable
		Organic pollutants	Stratification by land use and soil texture
Soil erosion			
Agriculture	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by water erosion	2t/ha/year for shallow soils (<70 cm depth)	Soil formation rate: 0.3-1.4t/ha/year
		4/ha/year for deeper soils (>70 cm)	Preliminary thresholds, derivation of site-adapted tolerable soil loss rates recommended
			The current indicator description in this report includes only soil erosion by water, whereas the threshold addresses all other erosion types
Soil biodiversity loss			
Loss of soil biodiversity (sub-indicators)	To be developed: exceedance of safe minimum standards of ecosystem conservation. Exceedance of operating ranges (OR) for specific soil animals and microorganisms		Requires sub-indicators by species and/or functional group

Soil compaction		
Harmful subsoil compaction (sub-indicators)		Priority (sub)-indicators: Saturated hydraulic conductivity (Ks)<10cm/day Air capacity (AC) <5% Exceedance of 'action' values (Zink et al.2011) Secondary sub-indicators with available thresholds: bulk density,internal soil strength, air permeability and oxygen diffusion.

Table 3. Overview of the main threats and their indicators (updated by EEA in Jan 2023)

Soil organic carbon

We can find two ways to show the organic carbon content of the soil. SOC content, expressed as the concentration of total fine-fraction organic carbon in C/kg or % and SOC stock (expressed in C/ha) , representing the pool of organic carbon for a specific layer of the soil. The quantification of this one relies on other variables as bulk density, coarse mineral fragments content and layer thickness.

Assessing soil health by establishing a SOC threshold to monitor is a challenging task. There has been much discussion about whether there is a common optimal or critical minimum SOM or SOC level (Goulding et al., 2013). This is because SOC content affects different soil properties in addition to the variability of soils around the world.

Cédric Deluz et al., 2020. proposes a double-diagonal SOC sampling method with 20 samplings for small-medium farmers as the best option to monitor SOC in situ.

Gholizadeh et al., 2018. showed the best SOC and Sentinel-2 spectral bands correlations (Random Forest modelling) from B4 and B5, followed by B11 and B12. Among all spectral indices, BI, BI2, GNDVI and SATVI provided the strongest correlations with SOC. Spectral models can be improved through the implementation of predictors such as vegetation, topography, climate and geology, knowing their high correlation with SOC. This dataset can be combined using machine learning to predict and monitor SOC with an acceptable spatial resolution, for better management and decision making in soil health.

Soil organic carbon is strongly correlated with other soil properties, in particular the clay content. According to several studies (Johannes et al. 2017, Fell et al., 2018, Prout et al. 2020, Schjøning et al., 2012) the SOC/clay ratio seems to be a valid indicator for monitoring soil structural stability, at least in soils dominated by 2:1 layer clay minerals. The ratio should be translated into a different threshold for other soils with differences in clay mineralogy.

According to the Soil Monitoring Report by the EEA, defining the ideal soil organic carbon (SOC) stocks is challenging, as it may vary depending on the site and the specific functions of the soil. Dedicated monitoring programs are required for organic soils and the depth of accumulated organic matter. While existing programs for monitoring soil organic carbon (SOC) in mineral soils are valuable, they should strive to improve their spatial resolution at the EU level. This should involve not only assessing bulk density, texture, and fine fraction carbon (<20µm, MAOM), but also incorporating data on yield differences and historical/current land use information.

Vegetation cover

Vegetation cover is a key factor in soil degradation and soil health. Threats such as soil erosion and degradation begin when parts of the surface are free of vegetation. A reduction in perennial vegetation cover is considered an

important indicator of the onset of desertification. Many authors have shown that vegetation cover plays a very important role in protecting the soil surface from raindrops, increasing soil organic matter, soil aggregate stability, water holding capacity, hydraulic conductivity, delaying and reducing surface water runoff, etc. Vegetation cover can be measured in different ways. In the field by assessing the percentage of the ground that is covered by existing vegetation or by earth observation techniques. This can be modified throughout the year, so we focus on the existing vegetation before the wet period, as this is where active soil erosion mainly takes place.

Raid Almalki et al., 2022 recommends the use of different vegetation indices that have been developed to predict changes in vegetation for different purposes. Each monitoring area will require the vegetation indices that suit it best, so the strengths and weaknesses of the different indices proposed should be measured (Table 4).

	Index	Reference
Multispectral Vegetation Index	Normalized Differences Vegetation Index (NDVI)	[Bannari, A.; Morin, D.; Bonn, F.; Huete, A. A review of vegetation indices. Remote Sens. Rev. 1995, 13, 95–120]& [Albalawi, E.K.; Kumar, L. Using remote sensing technology to detect, model and map desertification: A review. J. Food Agric. Environ. 2013, 11, 791–797]
	Enhanced Vegetation Index (EVI)	[Bannari, A.; Morin, D.; Bonn, F.; Huete, A. A review of vegetation indices. Remote Sens. Rev. 1995, 13, 95–120]& [Albalawi, E.K.; Kumar, L. Using remote sensing technology to detect, model and map desertification: A review. J. Food Agric. Environ. 2013,
	Soil Adjusted Vegetation Index (SAVI)	[Bannari, A.; Morin, D.; Bonn, F.; Huete, A. A review of vegetation indices. Remote Sens. Rev. 1995, 13, 95–120]& [Somvanshi, S.S.; Kumari, M. Comparative analysis of different vegetation indices with respect to atmospheric particulate pollution using sentinel data. Appl. Comput. Geosci. 2020, 7, 100032]
	Atmospherically Resistant Vegetation Index (ARVI)	[Bannari, A.; Morin, D.; Bonn, F.; Huete, A. A review of vegetation indices. Remote Sens. Rev. 1995, 13, 95–120] & [Somvanshi, S.S.; Kumari, M. Comparative analysis of different vegetation indices with respect to atmospheric particulate pollution using sentinel data. Appl. Comput. Geosci. 2020, 7, 100032]
	Ratio Vegetation Index (RVI)	Allbed, A.; Kumar, L. Soil salinity mapping and monitoring in arid and semi-arid regions using remote sensing technology: A review. Adv. Remote Sens. 2013, 2013, 41262.
	Green Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (GNDVI)	Allbed, A.; Kumar, L. Soil salinity mapping and monitoring in arid and semi-arid regions using remote sensing technology: A review. Adv. Remote Sens. 2013, 2013, 41262.
	Chlorophyll Index Green (CI green)	Sishodia, R.P.; Ray, R.L.; Singh, S.K. Applications of remote sensing in precision agriculture: A review. Remote Sens. 2020, 12, 3136.
	Difference Vegetation Index (DVI)	Sishodia, R.P.; Ray, R.L.; Singh, S.K. Applications of remote sensing in precision agriculture: A review. Remote Sens. 2020, 12, 3136.
	Chlorophyll Vegetation Index (CVI)	Sishodia, R.P.; Ray, R.L.; Singh, S.K. Applications of remote sensing in precision agriculture: A review. Remote Sens. 2020, 12, 3136.

	Optimized Soil Adjusted Vegetation Index (OSAVI)	Sishodia, R.P.; Ray, R.L.; Singh, S.K. Applications of remote sensing in precision agriculture: A review. <i>Remote Sens.</i> 2020, 12, 3136.
	Transformed Vegetation Index (TVI)	Allbed, A.; Kumar, L. Soil salinity mapping and monitoring in arid and semi-arid regions using remote sensing technology: A review. <i>Adv. Remote Sens.</i> 2013, 2013, 41262.
	Modified Transformed Vegetation Index (MTVI)	Allbed, A.; Kumar, L. Soil salinity mapping and monitoring in arid and semi-arid regions using remote sensing technology: A review. <i>Adv. Remote Sens.</i> 2013, 2013, 41262.
Hyperspectral Vegetation Index	Normalized Differences Vegetation Index (NDVI)	Morier, T.; Cambouris, A.N.; Chokmani, K. In-season nitrogen status assessment and yield estimation using hyperspectral vegetation indices in a potato crop. <i>Agron. J.</i> 2015, 107, 1295–1309.
	Enhanced Vegetation Index (EVI)	Liu, H.Q.; Huete, A. A feedback-based modification of the NDVI to minimize canopy background and atmospheric noise. <i>IEEE Trans. Geosci. Remote Sens.</i> 1995, 33, 457–465.
	Soil Adjusted Vegetation Index (SAVI)	Huete, A.R. A soil-adjusted vegetation index (SAVI). <i>Remote Sens. Environ.</i> 1988, 25, 295–309. [Google Scholar] [CrossRef]
	Atmospherically Resistant Vegetation Index (ARVI)	Bannari, A.; Morin, D.; Bonn, F.; Huete, A. A review of vegetation indices. <i>Remote Sens. Rev.</i> 1995, 13, 95–120.
	Transformed Difference Vegetation Index (TDVI)	Morier, T.; Cambouris, A.N.; Chokmani, K. In-season nitrogen status assessment and yield estimation using hyperspectral vegetation indices in a potato crop. <i>Agron. J.</i> 2015, 107, 1295–1309.
	Weigthed Difference Vegetation Index (WDVI)	Bannari, A.; Morin, D.; Bonn, F.; Huete, A. A review of vegetation indices. <i>Remote Sens. Rev.</i> 1995, 13, 95–120.
	Optimized Soil Adjusted Vegetation Index (OSAVI)	Morier, T.; Cambouris, A.N.; Chokmani, K. In-season nitrogen status assessment and yield estimation using hyperspectral vegetation indices in a potato crop. <i>Agron. J.</i> 2015, 107, 1295–1309.

	Modified Chlorophyll Absorption in Reflectance Index (MCARI)	Morier, T.; Cambouris, A.N.; Chokmani, K. In-season nitrogen status assessment and yield estimation using hyperspectral vegetation indices in a potato crop. Agron. J. 2015, 107, 1295–1309.
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Table 4. Overview of different indexes and references related. (Source: Raid Almalki et al., 2022)

Soil structure

The main threat related to soil structure is soil compaction and soil sealing. Soil compaction is one of the worst soil degradation, in addition to erosion and soil removal in agricultural soils, causing reduction in agricultural productivity. Several factors are responsible for soil compaction. Among them, poor soil management practices (high mechanical and tillage system), which destabilise the physico-chemical balance of the soil.

The bulk density is a parameter with high spatial and temporal variability because it is related to texture, aggregation, organic carbon content and water drainage. It is the most commonly used indicator to monitor soil structure. Air capacity (%) and soil texture are other factors for a correct assessment of soil compaction. If we look at the European Environment Agency's report, there are many more variables to take into account (Table 5). The following table would show the parameters according to complexity as well as the measurement methods:

Soil environment	Indicator	Soil property
Air regime	Air storage	Air capacity
		Bulk density
	Air flow	Pore continuity
		Oxygen diffusion
		Air permeability
Water regime	Water storage	Available water capacity
		Bulk density
	Water seepage	Hydraulic conductivity (saturated/unsaturated)
		Pore continuity
		Flux directions: isotropy/anisotropy
Thermal regime	Heat storage / Heat flux	Heat capacity and conductivity
		Thermal diffusivity
		Pore continuity
		Water content
Habitat for living organisms	Microbial composition	Diversity and community structure
	Abundance of functional species groups	Oxic/anoxic taxa and distribution (e.g. methanogens; sulphate-reducing bacteria or ectomycorrhizal fungi)

Physical soil regime: soil strength	Deformation status	Bulk density
		Proctor density (a)
		Average mean diameter Of aggregates
	Stress strain (b)	Stress Stress propagation
		Precompression stress
		Crushing strength
		Shear strength
		Ratio of precompression stress to actually applied
Changes in air, water, thermal flow processes and biological regimes due to stress strain and shear stress-induced distortion		
Root functions	Rootability	Root length and root surface density
	Nutrient availability	Penetration resistance

Table 5. *Soil indicators and properties for soil compaction.*

Source: EEA Soil monitoring in Europe 2022 doi: 10.2800/956606

Soil pollutants

Soil pollution is a serious concern that can arise from a variety of sources. The two main types of soil pollution are point source pollution and diffuse pollution. Point source pollution is caused by a single identifiable source, such as an industrial spill, while diffuse pollution comes from multiple sources, such as agricultural land management practices and atmospheric deposition.

Detecting the impact of pollutants due to diffusion is a complex process that requires careful monitoring over time. In most cases, the assessment of trends related to soil pollution is based on modelling techniques.

Heavy metals, such as lead, cadmium, and mercury, are some of the most common and damaging contaminants. These metals can accumulate in soil over time, leading to toxic levels that can harm plants, animals, and humans. They can also leach into groundwater, posing a threat to drinking water supplies. Another major group of soil contaminants is pesticides and herbicides, which are widely used in agriculture and landscaping. These chemicals can persist in the soil for years, affecting soil fertility and potentially contaminating water sources. Some pesticides have been linked to cancer and other serious health problems, making their presence in soil a significant public health concern. Industrial pollutants, such as petroleum products, solvents, and chemicals, can also contaminate soil. These substances are often released into the environment through spills, leaks, and improper disposal, and can have serious long-term effects on soil quality and fertility. In addition, radionuclides, which are radioactive materials that can occur naturally or as a result of human activities causing serious health problems, including cancer and genetic damage, and can persist in soil for thousands of years.

To manage and remediate polluted sites, several sub-indicators can be used, including soil polluting activity, the number of contaminated sites, progress in site management, expenditures on remediation, groundwater incidents, and dominant pollutants. Proper monitoring and management of these indicators can help prevent further soil pollution and ensure that polluted sites are remediated in a timely and effective manner (EEA,2022)

Soil biodiversity

Increasing soil biodiversity has positive impacts on almost all soil functions. Despite knowing many of the positive impacts of healthy soil biodiversity, there is a lack of knowledge about the status of soil biodiversity and how to quantify it correctly. A variety of biodiversity quantification methods exist, but sometimes most of them are not species-based due to the great diversity and lack of knowledge about the relationships between the different taxa found in the soil.

The French Soil Quality Monitoring Network initiative allowed the sampling of 1700 different points, enabling characterise microbial communities, bacterial biodiversity and microbial biomass, under different soil types and land uses. The LUCAS survey coordinated by the European Commission's Joint Research Centre included 2018 a soil biodiversity component including DNA

metabarcoding of bacteria, archaea, fungi and other eukaryotes. The ultimate aim of this was to characterise communities of soil organisms and identify species by associating them with soil properties, climatic conditions and land cover.

According to Aksoy et al. (2017), variables as pH, soil textural class, organic matter and land use/land cover are the “changeable” parameters with the highest importance to estimate the soil biodiversity potential. This potential can be mapped indirectly via proxies through these variables. Thresholds for these variables could be used to spatially delineate “risk” areas for certain soil faunal groups as earthworms, collembolans, etc (Table 7).

Indicator	Creamer et al. (2019)	Huberet al.(2008)	Breure (2004)
Diversity of earthworms	X	X	X
Diversity of collembolans		X	
Microbial biomass	X	X	X
Diversity of nematodes	X		X
Soil texture	X		
Bulk density	X		
Groundwater table depth	X		
pH	X		
C:N ratio	X		
N:P ratio	X		
Soil organic matter	X		
Organic carbon content	X		

Table 6. *Indicators for soil biodiversity proposed by different authors (EEA Soil monitoring in Europe 2022)*

Variable	Classes of parameters for scoring soil biodiversity potential			
pH	<4	4-5.2	5.2-8.2	>8.2
Soil textural class	Coarse	Medium	Medium-fine	Fine
Organic matter (%)	<1	<2	<3	>4
Potential evapotranspiration(mm)	<-500	until 500	>500	-
Annual average temperature (°C)	<5	5 to 20	>20	-
Soil biomass productivity	Poor	Average	Good	-
Land use/land cover	Artificial	Arable	Permanent crops	Others

Table 7. List of parameters with high importance to estimate soil biodiversity potential. (Source: Aksoy et al. (2017))

Soil acidification

Soil acidification is a serious threat to soil health that occurs when the acid neutralizing capacity of the soil is reduced, leading to a decrease in pH. This threat is mainly caused by the precipitation of sulphur dioxide, ammonia, and nitric acid, and has predominantly affected agricultural soils and forests. Furthermore, the acidity of soils can be caused by soil parent material, soils will become acidic after different lengths of time.

The use of ammonium fertilizers in agricultural soils is a major contributor to this problem. These compounds form nitrates and hydrogen ions, which decrease the availability of nutrients for plants.

The pH level of the soil is an important indicator of soil health as it is closely related to soil fertility and vegetation growth. When the pH level is very low, the availability of important nutrients such as calcium, magnesium, and potassium is limited, and the concentration of toxic elements such as aluminium, manganese, and cadmium can increase. This can lead to restricted growth of plants and soil microorganisms due to the lack of nutrient availability and metal toxicity. Soil acidification is also linked to reduced tree vitality, nutrition, and plant species diversity in forest undergrowth (EEA,2022)

In agricultural soils, pH and base saturation are the indicators commonly used to assess soil acidity status as they are related to nutrient availability and subsequent crop growth. However, some studies have shown a correlation between soil acidification, aluminium content, and dieback in forest soils. pH is a standardized soil health indicator that is widely used because it is easy to measure and study. A lot of literature exists that describes optimal plant growth thresholds according to pH, as well as average pH values according to soil type. Therefore, proper management of soil pH levels is critical to ensuring soil health and maximizing crop yields.

4.3 Policy conditions

The new **EU Soil strategy for 2030** sets the vision to have all soils in healthy conditions by 2050. It proposes a combination of voluntary and legislative action to help to achieve the objectives of the strategy. Soil health laws proposed in this new initiative will be complementary to the legislative proposal for EU targets to restore degraded ecosystems, especially those with the most potential to provide ecosystem services and to prevent natural disasters (COM (2021) 699 final).

The proposal identifies numerous aspects that should be regulated and considered. Most aspects relate directly to the NOVASOIL project, including: indicators of soil health, and its range of values, requirements for sustainable soil use, monitoring and reporting of soil condition, options for identifying, registering and remediating contaminated sites, etc.

In the time frame of the project, policy demands coming from the **European Green Deal, Farm to Fork strategy, Zero pollution action plan, Biodiversity strategy for 2030** and the new **EU Soil Health Law**, will be of relevance for the project. This project will be useful in reaching the targets of the **Sustainable**

Development Goals (SDGs) as SDG2, SDG6, SDG11, SDG13 and SDG15. All of these goals are related to soil health, and no one could be achieved without improving the management of the soil.

NOVASOIL will exploit existing tools and instruments, contributing to EU policies, such as environmental objectives of the **Common Agricultural Policy (CAP)**, The Habitats Directive; supporting global commitments to achieve land degradation neutrality in the EU by 2030, through innovation actions concerning with soil health and business models. The new CAP 2023-2027 is built around 10 key objectives, which focus on economic, social and environmental goals. As well as the other European and national policies, the European countries will implement the new CAP with a CAP Strategic Plan at the national level. Strategy plans will be adapted to the needs of each country and objectives will change according to their needs. Countries were required to produce a thorough assessment of what must be done based on a Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats (SWOT) analysis of their territory and agri-food sector. The key policy objectives are:

- to ensure a fair income for farmers;
- to increase competitiveness;
- to improve the position of farmers in the food chain;
- climate change action;
- environmental care;
- to preserve landscapes and biodiversity;
- to support generational renewal;
- vibrant rural areas;
- to protect food and health quality;
- fostering knowledge and innovation.

Other policies such as **LULUCF Regulation, National Emission Ceilings Directive, Eighth Environment Action Programme 2030** or the **Water Framework Directive** could influence this project.

4.4 Legal conditions

the will of NOSAVOIL project is to contribute to the strengthening of soil health legislation and to implement of sustainable business models that invest in improving soil health. Indeed, legal guarantees are essential to develop this kind of business. Currently, European environmental legislation covers some but not all environmental aspects. The degrees of legal protection for air or water are different from those for soil resources. Without strict laws to protect soil, all efforts to achieve the objectives of the European Green Deal (climate neutrality, biodiversity restoration, zero pollution or sustainable food systems) will be in vain.

To develop this, the EU needs to take into account the multi-functionality of soil and develop an advanced legislative framework on soil health. Following the objectives of the new EU Soil Strategy 2030, the EU Commission is set to table a proposal for a new legislative initiative on soil health, that responds to efforts to protect and restore soil from the multitude of threats facing soil in Europe through the new Soil Health Law. The goals of this legislation include improving soil quality, reducing soil degradation and erosion, and promoting the sustainable use of soil resources. The legislation also aims to improve soil data collection, assessment, and monitoring, and to increase awareness of the

importance of soil health. This new legislation builds upon the existing EU soil framework directive and other relevant EU laws. The following key aspects are going to be amended:

Principle of integration

The principle of integrating soil health within the European Union aims to merge soil protection with other policies such as agriculture, environment, and spatial planning. This principle acknowledges the interrelatedness of soil health and other environmental and socio-economic factors and endeavours to maintain a balance between the diverse functions and uses of soil. The primary objective is to guarantee that soil is managed sustainably, preserving its ecological and productive capacity for future generations. The EU's soil framework directive and other applicable legislation embody this principle (Kolpak et Fornabaio, 2022)

Principle of subsidiarity and soil protection

The subsidiarity principle of EU soil health emphasizes that decisions concerning soil protection should be made at the most suitable level of government, whether it be at the local, regional, national, or EU level. It enables the EU to exercise its powers when EU intervention is necessary to achieve its objective, but cannot be effectively accomplished at the Member State level. This principle is rooted in the belief that the individuals closest to the affected communities and environments are better suited to make decisions affecting soil health. The subsidiarity principle ensures that the EU does not intervene in areas where action is not needed, and enables national and local authorities to take the appropriate measures to safeguard soil health. It is unlikely that the EU Committee of the Regions will oppose the principle of subsidiarity in the Soil Health Law. The Committee has expressed its support for the EU Soil Strategy 2030 and its efforts to promote soil protection through a European framework. While the misuse of this principle has been used to obstruct the 2006 Soil Framework Directive, legislation on soil protection at the EU level is urgently required and would comply with the subsidiarity principle. The Soil Strategy for 2030 indicates that the new Soil Health Law will undergo a subsidiarity check, in accordance with Article 5 TEU requirements. The new Soil Health Law will be critical in filling the legislative gap that contributes to inadequate soil management practices and the consequent stress on soil. This aspect is crucial in establishing the legislative basis for each business model and regulating it in accordance with the location (Kolpak et Fornabaio, 2022).

Monitoring soil through LUCAS

Land use and Coverage Area frame Survey (LUCAS) is a method by The Statistical Office of the European Union (EUROSTAT) to gather information on land cover and land use. LUCAS is an essential tool to assess the impact on the environment and agriculture, serving to evaluate the state of the Common Agricultural Policy. In addition, it can be used to inform climate change adaptation and mitigation measures. It is key to generating climate indicators as well as biodiversity indicators, playing a fundamental role in the Soil Health Law. Data gathered through LUCAS Soil will ensure robust science-based decision-making, supporting the implementation of the law through

regular monitoring and reporting. Therefore, it will be essential to include LUCAS Soil in the Soil Health Law, providing big support for its functioning and regulating its uses, complemented with new technologies to improve the modelling and to achieve the European Green Deal targets. (Kolpak et Fornabaio, 2022).

4.5 Market situation

The market related to soil health and the goods that can be obtained from it is very varied. This wide range of possibilities in the market makes it difficult to define a clear-cut situation.

If we talk about payment for ecosystem services (PES) schemes, it must provide a win-win opportunity for both the supplier and buyers of the service. PES schemes succeed with a robust and credible business case and an accurate estimate of costs, including transactions. We can find different spatial scales. International, such as the mechanism for Reducing Emissions from Deforestation and Forest Degradation (REDD+), developed by different countries paying to avoid this degradation and reduce emissions; to local or national level, as watershed protections or incentives to land managers. One of the most widely used PES schemes is related to climate change mitigation through carbon credits. The market is quite developed around carbon credits and some other PES schemes (Bond, et al., 2013)

Good market access is one of the most powerful mechanisms for generating and investing in business models that are enthusiastic about improving soil health, especially in developing regions. For example, areas of relatively high agricultural potential but remote from major markets face numerous challenges in marketing their outputs. If there is a good market situation and market access, transaction costs will be low and profits in the business model will be transformed into substantial incomes.

If we go into more detail on PES schemes, the process that determines how to access the market and set prices involves different considerations. As explained in the PES feasibility guide (Fripp, 2014), it should be clarified whether it would be the producers of the service who accept the price adjusted by international markets, such as in the carbon market, or by an international body or entity as for a debt-for-nature swap. Or rather the price is negotiated depending on the buyer's willingness to pay for the service and the supplier's willingness to accept the price suggested by them. Defining the spatial level of the business model (ES will be sold internationally, nationally or locally?), which rules and how accessible it is, are fundamental steps to establish and implement PES. For example, if a user decides to sell carbon credits because the area in which he or she is interested is the most viable and efficient business model, she or he will need advice on how to access the international carbon market. Regarding the ecosystem service of carbon sequestration and climate mitigation, according to NGFS TSVCM McKinsey and Company, the global annual demand for carbon credits could amount to between 1.5-2 Gt of carbon dioxide by 2030 and up to 13 gTCO₂ by 2050. The latter would imply an increase in market size between \$5 billion - \$30 billion. However, several factors could make it difficult to mobilize the potential supply and bring it to the market. Furthermore, buyers and sellers face the

problem that high-quality carbon credit is scarce, due to time-varying carbon verification and quantification methodologies (Blaufelder et al., 2021).

An example of an integrated production business model is the “Flora Aromatica Santa Luce” project. This project involves 16 actors, 11 farmers, 2 research institutes, 1 farmers organisation and the commercial firm Flora. The goal was “create a new symbolic capital of the rural area at the borders between the provinces of Pisa and Livorno and valorize it as a new touristic destination” (Scaramuzzi et al., 2020), something like agro-tourism, but recognizing the importance of direct selling. This model is based on the agro-tourism market and supply chains around the lavender crop. This project is a good example of how to enrich the rural territorial capital in its social, environmental, human and symbolic components, also promoting the construction of a sustainable territorial model capable of self feeding with a specific tourism demand and economic development (Scaramuzzi et al., 2020).

In recent years, stakeholders in the agricultural sector have realized the importance of healthy soils and the importance of maintaining a stable yield crop, without degrading the soil, reducing costs and increasing ecosystem services. And this is not only for croplands, but also for forests, pastures, orchards, etc. Many areas of the world, including Europe, are under threat from different degradation factors such as soil loss, soil sealing, nutrient loss, droughts, etc. However, another way to invest in soil health is to implement management techniques that prevent soil degradation and, in turn, promote and increase the provision of ecosystem services. In the literature we find many case studies that implement certain soil management practices to bring soils to a better state. Soil degradation in sub-Saharan Africa is largely a result of prolonged crop cultivation without adequate return of organic matter or plant nutrients to replenish the soil. To improve these areas, the application of N fertilizers and cattle manure boosted maize yields and soil health, receiving more income for smallholders (Kihara et al., 2016). Another case is the olive farmers that are implementing cover cropping practices to improve biodiversity and reduce erosion, giving an example of integrated production (Bruggeman et al., 2008, WBCSD, 2018). The market situation of these cases is the same, only the costs and benefits obtained from the investment in soil health change. It is **an adaptation of the business model to the current climate change and soil pressure situation.**

A problem we encounter is that many ecosystem services are not sold on the market and no price that reflects the service’s economic value. This is a great opportunity to dive into the existing knowledge, and create and implement business models that in addition to the commonly quantifiable ecosystem services, can evaluate and give an economic value to those ES through valuation techniques. There is extensive literature for assessing the economic value of ecosystem services that are not on the market.

4.5.1 Market economic tools

In addition to the market situation, other important points to define are the forms or economic tools through which the business model could be regulated.

1.- Direct public payments: the government makes direct payments to providers of ecosystem services or environmental goods that improve soil health. The most common way to get the payment.

- Subsidies
- Prohibition of use
- Property use rights
- Mandatory farm set-asides
- Offsets
- Green bonds
- Direct Payment for Ecosystem Services
- Rewards for Ecosystem Services

2.- Direct private payment

- Offsets
- Corporate social responsibility
- Direct Payments for Ecosystem Services
- Rewards for Ecosystem Services

3.- Tax incentives: are a form of indirect government compensation for landowners protecting ecosystem services. Tax incentives are used, for instance, to encourage landowners in the United States to put their land under conservation easements.

- Conservation easements
- Taxes and charges

4.- Cap and Trade markets: the government or regulatory body first sets a limit or “cap” on the amount of environmental degradation or pollution allowed in a given area and then allows firms or individuals to meet the cap.

- Permits and quotas

5.- Voluntary markets: buyers and sellers engage in transactions voluntarily basis.

- Conservation easements
- Voluntary farm set-asides
- Green bonds
- Conservation concessions
- Rewards and Direct Payments for Ecosystem Services

6.- Certification programs: paying for the protection of ecosystem services by buying determined products (ecologically friendly products for example/ biological pesticides/not using chemicals in crops...)

- Marketing labels (certificates/sustainability standards)
- Marketing labels (without certificates or standards)
- Green bonds

4.5.2 Other actors

In this category we include at large other actors than agricultural, agroforestry, food and raw materials production firms that interact with the working of the bioeconomy system.

A central role may be played by consumers and by their willingness to pay for sustainable production, but an important player in the system may be relevant, especially public bodies and connecting institutions, such as NGOs, parks etc.

Other actors of the value chain may have an important role; e.g., input suppliers and processors of agricultural products.

The same applies to a variety of other actors, such as municipalities. Concerning the specific initiatives these categories can take the role of actors when they are actively involved in the action or as parties in the contract, or stakeholders, if they have a stake in it but are not directly active or contractually involved. Note that, in a circular bioeconomy and ecosystem services vision, the different social components are more and more interconnected and spatially related. As a result, besides individual actor groups and features, it is important to identify categories to qualify the whole system, much beyond agriculture and forestry, such as those proposed by the literature on socio-ecological systems.

4.6 Business features

4.6.1 Introduction

Business features refer to characteristics that can describe the business model type. It is well known that it is very difficult to describe all the possible business models and analyse them separately due to the great dimension of possibilities we are facing, as well as the state of innovation in which the project is located.

To relate the soil health concept fulfilling the objective of the project, creating business models that interact positively in this aspect. We identify the next set of features that models ought to follow (Commonland, 2017 & 2020)

- **Fundability:** models that argue their funding, in line with the Europe 2050 objectives and the market situation where they are situated, the trend over time, with a studied positive cost/benefit without administrative interests.
- **Profitability:** measured with incomes and expenses of the business model, positive cash flows have been generated for the restorative business case and/or there is room for reinvesting in the business
- **Feasibility:** reliable models, with a large life span, with semi-constant data that allows the assessment of the business model.
- **Assessability:** effective and possible monitoring, monitoring is carried out without aggressive practices, always in line with EU policies, understandable indicators to measure changes over time.
- **Replicability:** The methodologies are easily consultable, structured in a way that the same or similar actions can be replicated in other regions of future interest, with complete and organized information.

- **Sustainability:** follows the plans established in Europe, respects and even supports the new legislation and policies implemented on soil health and sustainable land use, is associated with climate change mitigation strategies, improved carbon, soil health, water and biodiversity.
- **Cooperativity:** understanding between stakeholders, smooth cooperation, no difficulties in the operationalisation of the business model, facilitation between land users and entities or persons interested in the implementation of the business model, awareness and participation. Networks, entrepreneurship and employment.

4.6.2 Feature used to identify business types in the project

We identified 4 main business models in the NOVASOIL project:

- **Payment for Ecosystem Services:** focused on obtaining direct or indirect benefits from ecosystem services (provided by the area where the model is implemented) through different market methods. All areas of interest that show potential in carbon sequestration services, water provision, erosion, flood control and cultural services are key to carrying out the model and for it to have a positive cost/benefit.
- **Value chain:** value chain types of contracts generally pay farmers in exchange for a particular product derived from environmental requirements attached to a contract for the provision of a private good, assuming that consumers are willing to pay for the public good when paying for the private good. Acceptability and cooperation among stakeholders is key to this type of model.
- **Carbon credits:** a carbon credit or carbon credit is a unit representing one ton of CO₂ equivalent absorbed or avoided in the atmosphere. These can be certified, but Europe is still working on unifying and standardising this section. Areas with ecological restoration potential are potential business models in this area, as large investors see the opportunity to contribute to climate change mitigation by promoting these actions.
- **Collective implementation:** the role of specific actors and the implementation of the model, especially the collaboration of collectives, cooperatives and farmer/farmer associations. The participation of key actors to carry out the provision of goods and services are important for the design of the type of contract in the model.

The categories described previously are not mutually exclusive and a mix of different business models can be found.

4.6.3 Other relevant features

Other payment characteristics

The most widespread parameter relevant for decision making is of course the level of payment. In addition to the form of payment and how it is connected to the established business model, other issues may arise such as the presence of bonuses or the timing of payments.

Actors/parties involved

Actors are the parties involved in the business model. This may include single actors, a group of actors, land users, multilevel actors. Scale of the business model e.g farm level, landscape level, watershed, region, etc, is also important in connection with the parties involved.

Monitoring and sanctions

Monitoring is responsible for assessing the status of the business and checking that it complies with the established requirements. If the results are not as expected, penalties are applied through a system of sanctions.

4.7 Mechanisms/processes

4.7.1 Conceptual and disciplinary references

On the disciplinary side, NOVASOIL entails an understanding of both individual and collective actions, as well as the study of how this translates into environmental and/or climate benefits. Behavioural aspects may be particularly relevant for the collective implementation of environmental conservation practices which requires horizontal coordination and action among independent landowners. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement GA 101091268 managers. In addition, monetary incentives (either individual or collective) coming from public policy may be not the only mechanism affecting decisions. While it is understandable that farmers have little incentive to continue the provision of practices related to soil health without payments, due to lack of remuneration by the market (Hodge, 2001), the literature also highlights the potential of vertical cooperation with soil ecosystem services valorisation through product chain strategies, payments for ecosystem services, market labels, etc, and the connection of beneficial soil management practices with social capital and innovation (Saxby, Gkartzios, and Scott, 2018). The literature also suggests that simple monetary assessment of incentives might fail to explain the emergence of cooperation (Ostrom, 1990). Institutional consideration, fairness in the distribution of benefits and costs, monitoring, and transaction costs are all elements that become relatively more important when the collective implementation of resource conservation is targeted.

The level of interaction is so crucial in these scenarios that, in some instances, the absence of one participant can result in complete failure, as the initial objective is not achieved. NOVASOIL provides a comprehensive approach to business model design that encompasses all the primary dimensions. This methodology involves comprehending four main aspects: a) mechanisms, typically addressed through economic incentives, simple behavioural assumptions, formal mathematical analysis, or mathematical modelling; b) expected behaviour of actors (e.g., farmers) concerning the proposed solutions, usually addressed using the theory of planned behaviour or behavioural economics, employing experiment-based instruments; c) institutional understanding of arrangements and solutions between stakeholders, which requires interfacing transaction cost economics, socio-ecological systems, legal perspectives, and collective action transitions; d) the effects on soil health and bundles of ecosystem services, as well as their

interaction, necessitating interfacing with sustainability and environmental sciences/landscape ecology.

NOVASOIL proposes a problem-oriented integration of these fields of expertise using a combination of selected instruments. Legal aspects (current legal framework and needed changes) will have a prominent role in the project in order to ensure the feasibility of business models in addition to guaranteeing the sustainability and soil health framework. The link between soil health policy programs and soil health indicators needs to be strengthened also through common methodological standards and structured databases. A specific emphasis will be put on the role of new technology, in connection with result-based payments and for involvement in chain valorisation. Most of the items listed in the mechanism's categories are somehow related to behaviour and decision making.

4.7.2 Costs/Benefits

The most classical economic basis to analyse behaviour is to consider the costs and benefits of the proposed business models. Costs and benefits for land users are the most common focus, but the public administration, chain actors, input providers, etc, should be taken into account too.

It is not only important to know the total costs and benefits, but to break down both concepts in all their forms helps to understand and analyse the different transactions that take place after the implementation of the models. The relevance of these transaction costs is huge, because it is a general issue in environmental policy (Coggan et al., 2010). Specifically private and public transaction costs in the form of administrative costs can be determinants for policy feasibility (EU Commission, 2019)

4.7.3 Acceptability

Generally, acceptability refers to the quality of a business model to be satisfactorily accepted by potential participants, specifically land users. This may be connected to some particular characteristic of the business models.

For example, cultural acceptability would be an important point to consider. Knowing what type of land user we are going to deal with. Birge and Herzon (2019) already distinguished 4 categories of farmers based on their integration of ecological results into farming, determined by nature values being: 1) central to farmer thinking 2) well-integrated 3) viewed positively with limited actions and, 4) mainly absent.

4.7.4 Preferences

Land users could show different preferences depending on business model attributes relevant to soil health. Preferences in landowners could change depending on the region where the possible business model is located. Acceptability and business model preference surveys could be created and circulated to land users in potential business model creation zones. The potential of surveys between landowners was tested by Cortés-Capano et al (2021), this type of methodology would be interesting to apply at the local level, to find business opportunities according to the behaviour of land users and potential investors.

4.8 Performance/evaluation

Considering the current situation with the development of new soil health policies, such as CAP 2023-2027, and the emphasis on innovative and sustainable solutions such as business models supported by scientific results, evaluation is a fundamental part of proving that a business model is viable in the context it is put forward.

A wide range of parameters that influence and define the performance of a business model have always been discussed in the literature. The design of future business models is a current topic of discussion that reiterates the importance of their compliance with environmental policies.

As expected, the main performance indicators are characterised by underlying criteria related with the above-mentioned policies. For example, effectiveness, as a parameter driven by the environmental effectiveness (if the business model complies with regulations and policies associated with the protection of the environment and its implementation does not negatively affect the “environment health”) and the cost-effectiveness, i.e, despite the business model complies with the environmental requirements, if it is not cost-effective for the actors involved, it could not be carried out. In addition to this parameter, the following list of performance indicators have been selected: longevity, social capital, acceptance, equity, profitability, compatibility, flexibility and targeting.

In many cases, the performance indicators are correlated, for example, if we have a business design where the life cycle and the stability are inappropriate, this aspect can have immediate effects on another indicator as effectiveness, reinforcing adversities to adopt the business model. For this, there is the process of evaluating the design of the business model, and a sort of “filter” that designs whose indicators pass this validity filter can be carried out.

4.9 Overview

The NOVASOIL project will adapt the classic CANVAS model (Osterwalder et al., 2010) to the soil health business models (Figure 3) in order to facilitate the comprehension of the business key elements. As it is indicated in Table 8, Osterwalder's canvas has nine boxes: customer segments, value propositions, channels, customer relationships, revenue streams, key resources, key activities, key partnerships, and cost structure. With the *business model design template*, a group of persons can easily describe its business model.

Figure 3 Business Canvas model design template: nine business model building blocks (Osterwalder et al., 2010).

The new version will be shown in the WP3 deliverables and forthcoming update of this framework.

4.10 List of potential performance indicators

Effectiveness

The effectiveness of the business model relies on two fundamental aspects: the environmental effectiveness and the "monetary" effectiveness of the model.

a) Environmental effectiveness

It can be defined as the level of care that the business model has with respect to natural capital, ecosystem services and the improvement of these compared to the initial moment of the model's implementation.

b) Cost-effectiveness

According to Batáry et al. (2015), the cost-effectiveness of solutions is defined by the relation between environmental outputs to cost (inputs), while costs to be potentially considered are program costs, transaction costs, farm implementation costs, etc.

Longevity

Estimated duration of the life cycle of the business model and its stability over time. In addition, the stability in the measurement of the monitoring data,

which allows to evaluate over time the trend of the model according to socioeconomic and environmental conditions.

Acceptance

Acceptance refers to the ability of stakeholders to understand the implications of the implementation of the model and its importance for soil health, while understanding the misconception of loss of benefits through unfamiliar sustainable management practices or unfamiliar business models. Acceptance is influenced by a broad number of endogenous and exogenous factors, such as framework conditions, behavioural aspects, education and obviously, knowledge.

Targeting

Bad targeting of business model objectives is a big criterion for low economic and environmental effectiveness (Robalino et al., 2008). Improved targeting involves the following aspects:

- Spatial targeting
- Cost/benefit targeting
- Structural targeting
- Environmental targeting

Flexibility

Increased flexibility enables the adaptation of business models to different context situations, conditions and challenges.

Equity/Fairness

Equity and fairness in the context of business models is a point to take into account when designing and implementing them. According to Schomers and Matzdorf, (2013), equity in the context of payments for environmental services includes three elements namely equity in access, equity in the outcome and fair payments. Perceived fairness is influenced mainly by the perception of risk, costs and benefits.

Compatibility

The design and implementation of the business model need to be situated according to the stakeholders and legal conditions where the system is to be created.

- Legal systems (new measures, national laws and regulations...)
- Business design of participants (the acceptance of the environmentally friendly measures by the land users)

Profitability

PES business models can be directly profitable for the land users as well as for other actors in the business model. In contrast, business models that don't cover the costs of management changes and therefore reduce the profitability of the involved actors are assumed to not be accepted.

Social/cultural capital

In addition to economic capital, this also exists in the form of social capital. For the ideals of investment in soil health and sustainable living to remain, the development of this social/cultural capital must be mobilized. This type of capital is transferable between its different forms (Burton and Paragahawewa, 2011). It found that the four components of social capital; trust, norms, connectedness and power, can all influence the decision of land users to change their soil management. Future research, policy and practice should consider whether a lack of effective social capital might hinder the adoption of new practices. Diversity is a good point; collaborative groups should work constructively together to build an effective social capital, where they can co-define and develop measures to sustainably manage soils (Rust et al., 2020).

- Trust: a key attribute of social capital which promotes collective action (La Porta et al., 2000; Tsai & Ghoshal, 1998). It relates to accepting information when deciding whether to start the “green” transition through more sustainable soil management practices (Rust et al., 2020).
- Connectedness: the configuration of social interactions, enabling the better exchange of knowledge. This is also influenced by social norms and how land users prefer to adhere to the status quo (Inman et al., 2018)
- Norms: if the norms within a land user community is to stick to the status quo, it will be difficult for them to deviate from established standards, but other measures such as financial incentives or policy regulations help to create change.
- Power: plays a decisive role with respect to social capital, designating who holds the most influential position in a network. The availability of information may vary depending on which entity or persons have the most influence within the business model. One of the ideas pursued by the project is equity among all the actors, since the correct collaborative action of all will make possible a more equitable and sustainable development (Rust et al., 2020).

5 Methods and stakeholder engagement

In general, involving stakeholders in designing business models can lead to several benefits, such as increased stakeholder engagement, better alignment of the business model with stakeholder needs and preferences, improved decision-making, and increased sustainability of the business model. It can also lead to a more comprehensive understanding of the business environment and the challenges and opportunities it presents.

Regarding initiatives to develop business models related to soil health and the incorporation of stakeholders, several initiatives have been carried out around the world. Some examples are:

- The Soil Health Institute (SHI): This US non-profit organization developed a business model for restoring soil health through collaboration between farmers, businesses, researchers and conservation groups. (Morgan, 2022; Morgan et al., 2022)

- Soil Association: This UK-based organization developed a business model for producing organic food and improving soil health by implementing sustainable practices (Poux & Aubert, 2018; Payton, 2021).
- Biome Makers: This California-based company developed a business model based on DNA sequencing to improve soil health and agricultural production through a better understanding of soil microorganisms (Acedo & Ferrero, 2021).
- SoilCares: This Netherlands-based agricultural technology company developed a business model for rapid and inexpensive measurement of soil nutrients to improve sustainable soil management (Ros et al., 2022).

The topic of stakeholder engagement has been extensively studied in recent years. Sterling and colleagues (2017) identified three primary forms of stakeholder engagement: externally driven, self-organized, and mixed. In their study, they identified various dimensions that impact the effectiveness of stakeholder engagement processes, emphasizing the importance of comprehending the governance and socio-cultural context across all forms of stakeholder engagement.

Several studies have suggested various approaches to incorporate research findings into the design process. For instance, Hassanzadeh and colleagues (2019) have proposed interactive modelling as a means of involving stakeholders in water management, along with providing a framework for stakeholder engagement.

6 Case studies management

6.1 Soil indicators selected

For each case study, careful consideration has been given to the selection of key soil indicators that will provide measurable insights into soil health, productivity, and sustainability. These indicators have been selected based on their relevance to soil functions, their ability to reflect changes over time, and their applicability across different biogeographical zones in an easy way. Additionally, they were selected based on their potential to measure or monitor specific soil threats. NOVASOIL case study leaders will compile soil information based on the indicators and laboratory methods proposed according to their budget and relevance for the case study:

- **Trace elements** (mg/kg) such as aluminium (Al), cadmium (Cd), lead (Pb), zinc (Zn), and sulphur (S) are essential in monitoring soil contamination and pollution levels, particularly heavy metals. These elements, when present in excess, can be toxic to plants, microorganisms, and even humans through the food chain. Monitoring their concentrations allows us to assess the risk of heavy metal contamination, which can inhibit plant growth and reduce microbial activity, affecting overall soil health. Laboratory method proposed: ICP-OES/Dig.Ác.- ICP-OES/MIII/-.

- **Macroelements (mg/kg)** like nitrogen (N), phosphorus (P), potassium (K), magnesium (Mg), calcium (Ca), and sodium (Na) are fundamental nutrients required for plant growth. An imbalance in these elements, whether through deficiency or excess, can lead to reduced fertility, soil degradation, and even environmental issues such as eutrophication (especially from excess nitrogen and phosphorus) and salinization (due to sodium accumulation). Additionally, is related with other soil indicators as SAR or ESP. Laboratory method proposed: ICP-OES/MIII - Kjeldahl/-.
- **Microelements (mg/kg)**, including boron (B), iron (Fe), copper (Cu), zinc (Zn), and manganese (Mn) are crucial for various plant metabolic processes. Insufficient levels of these micronutrients can lead to decreased crop productivity, reduced plant health, and diminished soil fertility. Laboratory method proposed: ICP-OES/MIII.
- **Nitrates (mg/kg)** are an important indicator of nitrogen availability in the soil. High nitrate concentrations, however, may signal over-fertilization or pollution. Nitrates are prone to leaching into groundwater, which can cause environmental issues such as eutrophication in aquatic systems and pollution of drinking water sources. Laboratory method proposed: UV-Vis/-
- The **Sodium Adsorption Ratio (SAR)** is a critical indicator of the relative concentration of sodium in comparison to calcium and magnesium. It is particularly important in assessing the risk of soil salinization, as high SAR values can lead to poor water infiltration, soil dispersion, and sodium toxicity. Laboratory method proposed: Calculation
- The **Exchangeable Sodium Percentage (ESP)** measures the proportion of sodium in the soil's exchange complex. A high ESP value suggests that sodium is accumulating in the soil, which can degrade soil structure, reduce its permeability, and hinder plant root development. Laboratory method proposed: Calculation
- **Cation Exchange Capacity (CEC)** represents the soil's ability to retain and supply essential cations to plant roots. Soils with higher CEC values are better able to hold onto nutrients, making them more fertile and productive. Low CEC soils, on the other hand, may struggle to retain essential nutrients, leading to nutrient leaching and reduced soil fertility. Laboratory method proposed: Calculation
- **Electric Conductivity (EC)** is used to assess soil salinity by measuring the soil's ability to conduct an electrical current. High EC values indicate elevated salinity levels, which can hinder plant water uptake, affect microbial activity, and reduce soil fertility, ultimately leading to soil degradation. Laboratory method proposed: Conductivity meter in soil-water extracts
- **Clay Content (%)** affects the soil's ability to retain water and nutrients, as well as its structure. Higher clay content improves water retention and nutrient holding capacity but may lead to soil compaction and poor aeration if improperly managed. Laboratory method proposed: Hydrometer
- **Silt Content (%)** is a key component of soil texture, influencing water retention and fertility. Soils with high silt content are more prone to erosion

due to their fine particles and less stable structure. Laboratory method proposed: Hydrometer

- **Bulk Density (g/cm³)** is an indicator of soil compaction and porosity. Higher bulk density often indicates compacted soil, which has reduced pore space for air and water, limiting root growth and increasing the risk of erosion. Laboratory method proposed: Calculation
- **USDA Soil Classification** is used to identify the soil type based on physical and chemical properties. Understanding the soil classification helps in selecting appropriate management practices land use. Laboratory method proposed: Based on the USDA Soil Taxonomy system using field observations and laboratory analysis.
- **pH** is a fundamental indicator of soil acidity or alkalinity, which affects nutrient availability and microbial activity. Extremes in pH can lead to nutrient deficiencies or toxicities, as well as impact soil biological processes, making it crucial to maintain pH within an optimal range for plant growth. Laboratory method proposed: Potentiometer (pH-meter)
- **C/N Ratio** measures the balance between total carbon and total nitrogen in soil. It provides insights into the rate of organic matter decomposition and nutrient cycling. A well-balanced C/N ratio supports healthy decomposition processes, while an imbalance may slow down these processes, impacting soil fertility. Laboratory method proposed: Calculation through total C and N ratio
- **Organic Matter (%)** is a key indicator of soil health as it influences soil structure, water retention, and nutrient availability. High levels of organic matter promote soil fertility and resilience, whereas the loss of organic matter results in degradation, poor soil structure, and increased vulnerability to erosion. Laboratory method proposed: Vol. Redox / Ignition method.
- **Organic Carbon (%)** reflects the carbon sequestered in the soil and is a critical indicator of soil's capacity to store carbon and support microbial life. Maintaining high levels of organic carbon is essential for promoting soil fertility and mitigating climate change through carbon sequestration. Laboratory method proposed: Vol. Redox / Ignition method.
- **Field Capacity (%)** measures the maximum amount of water the soil can hold after excess water has drained away. Soils with low field capacity may suffer from drought stress, while soils with overly high field capacity may become waterlogged, impacting root health and plant growth. Laboratory method proposed: Calculation
- **Available Water (%)** indicates the amount of water that plants can access within the soil. Insufficient available water can lead to drought conditions, resulting in poor plant growth and increased soil vulnerability to degradation. Laboratory method proposed: Calculation
- **Saturation (%)** is a measure of how much of the soil's pore space is filled with water. High saturation can lead to waterlogging, suffocating plant roots and creating conditions that promote soil erosion and structural collapse. Laboratory method proposed: Calculation

- **Wilting Point (%)** represents the soil moisture level at which plants can no longer extract water. When the soil moisture drops below this level, plants experience drought stress, and if prolonged, crop failure may occur. Laboratory method proposed: Calculation
- **Nematode Diversity**, specifically saprophytic and phytopathogenic nematodes, are important biological indicators of soil health. High quantity of saprophytic nematodes could increase the organic matter in the soil, enhance the fertility, microbial activity, etc. Laboratory method proposed: Microscopic identification
- **Fungi Diversity** provides critical insights into the soil's microbial health. Fungi play essential roles in nutrient cycling, organic matter decomposition, and soil structure. A reduction in fungal diversity may indicate ecosystem degradation, while the presence of specific fungal pathogens may signal a risk to certain plants. Laboratory method proposed: Microscopy to identify fungal genus and family.
- **Tree Cover and Ground Cover (%)** are physical indicators that help assess soil protection from erosion and the overall land management practices. Loss of ground cover increases erosion risk, reduces organic matter inputs, and accelerates the degradation of soil health. Measure the changes of the vegetation cover in pilot sites through the time allow to take decisions over the business models. Laboratory method proposed: Calculation

The use or measurement of other complementary indicators, in addition to those presented above, may be employed if they allow for a deeper understanding of any specific soil threat. Along with the soil indicator information, each case study must include environmental data about pilot site. In the following table, CS

Partner	Country	Coord X	Coord Y	Altitude (m.a.s.l.)	Biogeographical Zone
---------	---------	---------	---------	---------------------	----------------------

leaders will
found the
extra
information
to
complete.**CS
name**

Tamarguillo Park	Evenor	Spain	37.410206	-5.9061	25	Mediterranean
Pedoclimatic Zone	Mean annual temperat ure (°C)	Mean annual precipitati on (mm)	Mean Annual evapotranspira tion (mm)	Soil Type	Actual Main Land Use	Last Main Land Use
Mediterranean semi-arid	17.23	520	700	Regoso ls	Urban area	Arable land

Table 8. Template for NOVASOIL case study leaders

6.2 Impact evaluation of practices

To effectively evaluate the impact of a specific management practice on soil health, a comprehensive monitoring program will be implemented. This program will involve the systematic collection and analysis of data on key soil health indicators both before and after the implementation of the practice. By comparing these datasets, it will be possible to quantify the changes in soil health and attribute them to the specific management practice.

The selection of soil health indicators will be tailored to the specific land use and management practice under investigation. For instance, in agricultural settings, indicators such as organic matter content, pH, and nutrient availability will be prioritized. In forested areas, soil depth, cation exchange capacity, and biodiversity indicators will be given greater emphasis. A combination of physical, chemical, and biological indicators will be considered to provide a comprehensive assessment of soil health.

Baseline Data Collection

Prior to implementing the management practice, baseline data will be collected from multiple sampling locations within the study area. Soil samples will be collected at various depths to account for vertical variability. These samples will be analysed to determine the initial status of soil health with respect to the selected indicators.

The information will be collected and arranged according to soil depth. The topsoil will be considered as the first 15 cm of soil, and the subsoil will be from 15 cm onwards. This would be defined as Topsoil (0-15 cm) and Subsoil (>15 cm), where typically the subsoil is determined to extend to around 30 cm. For sample collection, the standards followed by the laboratories of each partner will be adhered to, with an effort to align with the methodologies mentioned

earlier. Furthermore, each case study leader should complete the information of Table X, as complement of soil analysis.

Monitoring and Data Collection

Following the implementation of the management practice, regular monitoring will be conducted. Soil samples will be collected from the same sampling locations at predetermined intervals to track changes in soil health over time. The frequency of sampling will depend on the dynamics of the soil and the expected rate of change in response to the management practice. The recommendation is take 2 replicates at least for each soil sampling point.

The most common approach is to monitor variables that change little over time through biannual sampling. Variables such as organic carbon, pH, nitrates, etc., would fall into this group. Variables like clay content, USDA classification, silt, or bulk density are those that change very little over time and would only be sampled after applying a soil management practice or following a specific event that affects soil structure. Finally, variables such as ground or tree cover, nematode diversity, or variables related to soil moisture content would be sampled seasonally. This approach increases our understanding of the dynamics of the case study.

Additionally, with the coordinates of the case study, monitoring can be implemented through Earth observation techniques, allowing us to cross-reference ground truth data with spectral information.

Data Analysis

The collected data will be subjected to statistical analysis to identify significant differences between the baseline and post-treatment measurements. Statistical tests such as t-tests and ANOVA will be employed to compare means and assess the magnitude of changes in soil health indicators. Correlation analysis will be used to explore relationships between changes in soil health indicators and specific aspects of the management practice.

Additionally, the soil data generated will be publicly reviewed through a Google Sheets platform where all collected data will be uploaded for storage. This allows for open access and transparency, enabling stakeholders and interested parties to track the progress and results of the study in real-time.

Interpretation and Reporting

The results of the data analysis will be interpreted in the context of the specific management practice and local conditions. Changes in soil health indicators will be compared to established benchmarks or reference values to assess the degree of improvement or degradation. The findings will be presented in a clear and concise manner, highlighting the strengths and limitations of the study. The results obtained will be included in the factsheets and the Final framework.

However, to estimate soil health in the case studies, metrics must be defined. According to the ongoing discussions promoted by the EC and initiatives such

as BENCHMARKS, NOVASOIL project will consider the following thresholds (it could be modified along the project):

Soil threats	Indicator	Thresholds	Land use
Soil Organic Carbon loss	Falling below optimal SOC level	Light soils: <1.2% SOC Medium soils: 1.2-1.9% SOC Heavy soils: >1.9% SOC	Cropland
Nutrient loss	Exceedance of critical levels of mineral nitrogen (agricultural land)	NH ₃ in air: 1-3mg NH ₃ /m ³ ; NO ₃ in groundwater: 50mg NO ₃ /l; N in surface water: 1.0-2.5mg N/l	Agriculture
Nutrient loss	N limitation based on exceedance of C:N ratio	C: N ratio 20-25; Leakage from forests: 1m	Forest land
Nutrient loss	Falling below optimal phosphorus	P concentration: 25-35mg/kg (optimal)	Agriculture
Nutrient loss	P limitation based on exceedance of N:P ratio	N:P ratio >18 (coniferous forests); N:P ratio >25 (deciduous forests)	Forest land
Acidification	Exceedance of critical pH levels	pH<4.5 -4.7 (critical); pH<5-5.5 (avoid)	Agriculture
Acidification	Exceedance of critical inorganic Al levels	Base cation: Al ratio= 1 (0.5-2.0)	Forest land
Soil pollution	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from heavy metals and organic pollutants	Cd, Cu, Pb, Zn, As, Hg, Ni, Cr; Organic pollutants	All land uses
Soil erosion	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by water erosion	2t/ha/year for shallow soils (<70 cm depth); 4/ha/year for deeper soils (>70 cm)	Agriculture

Table 9. Thresholds proposed to be applied in the NOVASOIL Case Studies (based on BENCHMARKS, Thresholds values from EU Soil Monitoring Law, etc)

6.3 Technologies for soil health business models

A comprehensive methodology will be implemented to monitor soil health and the performance of associated business models in the NOVASOIL case studies. Data will be collected from various sources, including maps, samplings, and customer surveys. This data will undergo rigorous analysis to identify patterns and trends.

Through the use of visualization tools, such as graphs and maps, results will allow to monitor the correct implementation of the business model. As well as, this information may be shared to the WP3 leader to be included in the final tool-box. The insights gained will be used to make informed decisions that optimize operations, enhance products and services, and ensure the long-term sustainability of the business.

To carry out this monitoring, specialized tools will be employed, including:

- **Geographic Information Systems (GIS):** To create maps and analyse spatial data.
- **Data analysis software:** To process large datasets and identify patterns.
- **Visualization tools:** To present results in a clear and concise manner.

6.4 Incentives and monetization in the case studies

Within the NOVASOIL project, a detailed analysis of the primary incentives for each case study will be conducted in task 3.1 of work package 3. Case study leaders, advised by NBU (task leader), will identify these incentives. Subsequently, the relevance of each incentive will be assessed, and potential new incentives will be explored. This analysis will enable the determination of the most relevant incentives and the prioritization of those that promote participation in these business models. Furthermore, the results could influence the development of new public policies that foster these incentives. The findings will be integrated into the deliverable of work package 3 and the final project tool.

To evaluate the monetization of soil health indicators across the main four business models described (collective implementation, value chain, carbon credits and payment per ecosystem services) a implementation plan has been designed based on the specific NOVASOIL case studies. The plan will measure, analyze, and monetize these indicators under different agroecological conditions, agricultural practices, and market structures in collaboration with WP2 and WP4.

The soil health indicators proposed previously will be measured in selected case studies in line with the Choice Experiments expected in WP2 and WP4 (focused on consumers and landowners). Those indicators with direct economic implications, such as organic matter content (carbon credits and productivity), water retention capacity (cost reduction and ecosystem services), soil biodiversity (productivity and certification), soil erosion (cost savings and ecosystem damage prevention), carbon sequestration capacity (carbon credits), and agricultural yields (income and cost reduction) will be prioritized. Each type of business model will be evaluated to how improved

soil health enhances productivity and reduce costs in agricultural production (value chain model), financial viability of soil carbon capture (Carbon credit model) and assess payments for providing ecosystem services (Payment per ecosystem service).

A comprehensive analysis will be carried out to assess the economic viability of each business model, considering implementation costs, financial benefits, and return on investment.

In the value chain models the assumption is that healthy soils improve nutrient cycling, water retention, and microbial activity, resulting in higher crop yields. This translates to increased revenue for farmers, especially when implementing practices such as crop rotation, reduced tillage, and organic amendments. The expected monetization is the increase of incomes from higher yields and lower input costs. As well as, certified products may have higher-value markets and price premiums.

In the carbon credits the assumption is that practices like no-till farming, cover cropping, agroforestry, and organic matter additions increase soil organic carbon. This carbon can be quantified and sold as carbon credits in voluntary or compliance markets. Regarding monetization selling carbon credits, typically measured in tons of CO₂ equivalents will be considered as incomes.

Finally, regarding payment per ecosystem services, the payment will depend of the ecosystem service' target. Healthy soils improve water infiltration, reduce runoff, and enhance water storage. This benefits downstream water users by providing cleaner water and reducing the risk of flooding or drought. On the other hand, agricultural landscapes with high biodiversity, supported by healthy soils, provide habitats for pollinators and beneficial insects. In addition, healthy soils improve soil structure and reduce erosion, contributing to landscape stability and reducing the costs of land degradation. So, the expected monetization could be related to payments from environmental NGOs or governments involved in biodiversity offset, payments from municipalities or water utilities for maintaining healthy soils' practices or compensations

7 Discussion, conclusions, and the next steps

The purpose of this document is to establish a preliminary conceptual framework for the NOVASOIL project. The initial and intermediate drafts of this framework have been instrumental in facilitating initial coordination among the project's working groups. In particular, this effort has provided support for WP2 in exploring existing business models, laid the foundation for understanding key incentives in WP3, and facilitated the identification of key actors and stakeholders for WP5.

The definition of soil health requires providing a range of values under different scenarios of soil types, land uses, and climatic zones to first distinguish between healthy and unhealthy soil, and secondly, to define strategies to improve physical, chemical, and biological variables that result in

healthy soil. The literature highlights ongoing research efforts to define these thresholds under various conditions (EEA, 2023).

The report "Soil monitoring in Europe: Indicators and thresholds for soil health assessments" provides a review of recent achievements and future perspectives of soil monitoring in Europe. The report emphasizes the importance of soil monitoring for environmental protection and food security, and highlights the need for an integrated approach to assessing soil health. The report also underscores the need to improve the availability and quality of soil monitoring data across Europe, as well as the need for greater coordination and collaboration among EU member states and stakeholders. Recent achievements include the development of soil quality monitoring systems, the establishment of a soil monitoring network at the European level, and the identification of specific areas of concern regarding soil health. The report concludes that soil monitoring is essential for ensuring sustainable soil management and protecting the biodiversity and ecosystem services that depend on soil.

Some bullet points highlighted from this report are:

- Soil monitoring is crucial to protect the environment and food safety.
- An integrated approach is necessary for soil health assessment.
- Quality and availability of soil monitoring data need to be improved throughout Europe.
- Greater coordination and collaboration among EU member states and stakeholders are required.
- Recent achievements include the development of soil quality monitoring systems, the establishment of a European soil monitoring network, and the identification of specific areas of concern regarding soil health.
- Soil monitoring is essential to ensure sustainable soil management and protect biodiversity and ecosystem services that depend on soil.

The article presents a framework for soil monitoring in Europe and highlights the following key indicators:

- Soil organic matter content: important for soil fertility and water retention.
- Soil erosion: soil erosion can affect water quality and soil's ability to store carbon.
- Soil compaction: soil compaction can decrease the ability of soil to retain water and nutrients.
- Soil contamination: soil contamination by chemicals, heavy metals, and other pollutants can be harmful to human health and the environment.
- Land cover change: changes in land cover can affect soil biodiversity and productivity.

In addition, the article emphasizes the importance of measuring these indicators systematically and consistently in order to assess soil health and take actions to improve it.

The direct follow-ups of this document will be in:

- D1.3 Draft framework in month 18.
- D1.4 Final framework un month 36.

Deliverable 1.3 "Draft Framework" differs from the present document in the following terms. This document includes a set of definitions and indicators related to soil health models that will be considered in the following project tasks.

On the other hand, Deliverable 1.3 presents a set of success stories as well as the main advances in the rest of the WPs to facilitate the design and implementation of business models. The following sections will be considered for this deliverable: sector needs and demands; management practices related to soil health; social innovation and incentives available for different business models in different European countries.

The final version of the framework will be designed as a guide and will bring together all the knowledge generated to carry out the implementation of a soil health business model and what factors must be considered. Additionally, it will include an update of the project's case studies, showing the impact of soil health.

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